

**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF OVERCOMING TYPES OF
DYSLEXIA IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN**

Rakhmatdjanova Nargiza Numanovna
Master's Student, 2nd Year, Special Pedagogy
Kimyo International University in Tashkent
Raxmatdjanova@mail.ru

Abstract

This article examines the types of dyslexia observed in primary school children and analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations for overcoming them. Dyslexia is one of the urgent issues in modern pedagogy and special education, as its timely identification and effective organization of correctional work have a positive impact on the learning process of pupils. The study highlights phonemic, optical, semantic, and other forms of dyslexia, as well as provides a scientific analysis of theoretical and methodological approaches applied to its remediation.

Keywords: dyslexia, phonemic dyslexia, optical dyslexia, semantic dyslexia, reading, correctional work, theoretical-methodological approach, speech therapist.

**ТЕОРЕТИКО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРЕОДОЛЕНИЯ ВИДОВ
ДИСЛЕКСИИ У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ**

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются виды дислексии, встречающиеся у младших школьников, а также анализируются теоретико-методологические основы их преодоления. Проблема дислексии является одной из актуальных направлений современной педагогики и специального образования, так как её своевременное выявление и эффективная организация коррекционной работы положительно влияют на процесс усвоения знаний учащимися. В исследовании выделены фонематическая, оптическая, семантическая и другие формы дислексии, а также проведён научный анализ теоретико-методологических подходов, применяемых для её преодоления.

Ключевые слова: дислексия, фонематическая дислексия, оптическая дислексия, семантическая дислексия, чтение, коррекционная работа, теоретико-методологический подход, логопед.

Human development occurs through speech; therefore, an individual must possess both internal and external speech capacity. According to statistical data, nearly 50 percent of children entering the first grade have oral speech disorders, and later they often develop written language impairments such as reading and writing difficulties. This indicates that one of the urgent issues of our time is the annual increase in the number of children with speech disorders.

Speech impairments, in turn, slow down the acquisition of reading skills, which play a crucial role in the development of a child's psyche. As many researchers have emphasized, reading is a form of oral speech, and its impairment has a significant impact on the educational process: the child perceives learning material with greater difficulty, which negatively affects the level of academic achievement. This has been noted in the scientific works of B.G. Ananyev, V.G. Goretskiy, T.G. Egorov, G.A. Kashe, R.I. Lalaeva, R.E. Levina, L.I. Tikunova, and other scholars.

One of the most important tasks of speech therapy with primary school children who have underdeveloped oral and written language is the development of reading skills. The regularity and purposeful orientation of speech therapy work directly influence not only speech development but

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-10

also the child's psychological and personal growth, as well as success in further schooling. Our research is devoted to the analysis of speech therapy and correctional work aimed at overcoming reading disorders in primary school pupils with general speech underdevelopment studying in general education schools.

According to A.R. Luria's research, reading is the process of transferring graphic symbols (distinguishing and recognizing letters) into the articulatory system (pronouncing words and reading them). On this basis, decoding occurs first, followed by comprehension of the text [5, p. 17].

The acquisition of reading skills by a child occurs gradually and consists of the following stages:

- **Preparatory stage** – children become familiar with letters and acquire the mechanism of reading;
- **Analytical reading stage** – children read syllable by syllable, and understanding the text requires rereading;
- **Synthetic reading stage** – the child reads words as whole units, visual perception of the word and its pronunciation are combined with comprehension of the text, though not yet completely;
- **Final automation stage** – reading skills become automated, and silent (internal) reading predominates.

The successful acquisition of this complex skill requires a number of conditions: well-formed sound pronunciation, the ability to conduct phoneme-letter and lexical-grammatical analysis and synthesis, developed spatial-temporal representations, well-formed processes of analysis, synthesis, and sequencing, as well as the child's ability to concentrate, distribute, and shift attention.

According to the clinical-psychological approach, the term "*dyslexia*" refers to a persistent and selective inability to acquire reading skills despite a child's adequate intellectual and speech development, the absence of auditory and visual impairments, and the presence of optimal learning conditions.

R.I. Lalaeva distinguishes the following types of dyslexia: phonemic, semantic, optical, mnemonic, agrammatic, and tactile [3, p. 100].

- **Phonemic dyslexia** is associated with underdevelopment of the phonemic system and sound-letter analysis. The child experiences difficulties in mastering letters, substitutes acoustically and articulatorily similar sounds, demonstrates an underdeveloped phonemic analysis, and shows distortions in the phonemic-syllabic structure of words.
- **Semantic dyslexia** manifests itself in impaired comprehension of the text while technical reading remains intact. This disorder is explained by difficulties in sound-syllabic synthesis and insufficient differentiation of representations concerning syntactic relations in sentences. As a result, the child may fail to understand the content of the text while reading syllabically, and consequently, cannot recognize or integrate segmented words into a meaningful whole.
- **Optical dyslexia** is characterized by difficulties in mastering graphically similar letters, mixing them up, or substituting them. This condition is associated with underdeveloped optical-spatial perception and representations, disturbances in visual gnosis, as well as in the processes of analysis and synthesis, and poorly differentiated representations of shapes. In cases of organic brain damage, the phenomenon of "mirror reading" is often observed.
- **Mnemonic dyslexia** manifests itself in difficulties in mastering letters and undifferentiated substitutions. The child fails to establish stable associations between sounds and letters, and speech memory is impaired. The child experiences difficulties in reproducing sequences of 3–5 sounds or words, and even if reproduction occurs, distortions in sound order or omissions are observed.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-10

- **Agrammatic dyslexia** is associated with underdevelopment of the grammatical structure of speech. It is most frequently observed in children with systemic speech underdevelopment. The child makes mistakes in using case endings and their agreement: for example, instead of “an interesting book” says “the book is interesting,” or instead of “good boys” says “boys are good.” Incorrect usage of endings is also observed: for instance, saying “notebook ours” instead of “our notebook.”

- **Tactile dyslexia** is observed in visually impaired children and is manifested in difficulties with tactile differentiation of Braille symbols. Such children tend to confuse letters that have the same number of dots, mirror-symmetrical placement of dots, or differ only by a single dot. Each letter is perceived in isolation, and therefore, an analytical approach predominates in their perception.

Characteristic features of oral speech in children with dyslexia include articulation defects, limited vocabulary, and insufficient precision in understanding and using words [1].

To identify dyslexia in a child, it is first necessary to consult a speech therapist (logoped). The speech therapist should begin by studying the child’s anamnesis, the characteristics of speech development, the condition of the articulatory apparatus, and motor skills. It is also important to analyze the child’s level of mastery of the native language. After that, the speech therapist conducts a diagnostic assessment of oral and written speech. However, speech therapy diagnostics alone are not sufficient—the child must also be examined by a neurologist and an ophthalmologist.

Once the diagnosis is confirmed, treatment should begin immediately. Therapy is not limited to speech therapy and correctional work. As a rule, a neurologist or neuropathologist prescribes medications that support the development of higher mental functions.

In working on the remediation of dyslexia, the speech therapist must adhere to a number of principles (R.I. Lalaeva):

- **Principle of complexity** – speech therapy should address all existing speech disorders.
- **Principle of considering pathogenesis** – methods applied must be directed toward eliminating the underlying mechanism of the disorder.
- **Principle of accounting for manifestation and severity** – the therapist must consider the child’s current stage of reading acquisition and the severity of symptoms.
- **Principle of indirect pathways** – based on the theory of functional systems.
- **Principle of gradual mental development** – skills that support reading development must be formed gradually.
- **Principle of gradual complication of tasks and speech material** – the child begins with simple exercises, gradually progressing to more complex ones.
- **Principle of systematicity** – dyslexia correction consists of a system of methods and techniques aimed at overcoming the core deficit.
- **Ontogenetic principle** – requires consideration of the sequence of speech function development in ontogenesis [3, p. 99].

For correctional-speech therapy work to be effective, exercises must correspond to the type of dyslexia:

- **In phonemic dyslexia** – correction of sound pronunciation and formation of concepts about the sound-letter structure of words.
- **In semantic dyslexia** – expansion of vocabulary and development of syllabic synthesis.
- **In optical dyslexia** – development of visual analysis and synthesis.
- **In agrammatic dyslexia** – the formation of grammatical constructions and speech structures in primary school children plays an essential role. In this process, exercises such as “*Finish the*

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-10

sentence” serve as an effective tool. In this task, the child is presented with pictures and must complete a sentence based on them, using correct grammatical structures.

Despite the diversity of methods and exercises aimed at overcoming dyslexia, the effectiveness of the correctional process directly depends on the specialists’ comprehensive and systematic approach. At the same time, it is essential to regularly reinforce the skills acquired in speech therapy sessions under parental supervision at home. Another important factor determining the success of correctional work lies in the principles applied by specialists in their practice. Since the process of reading is one of the key factors that determine a student’s academic success, the early identification of dyslexia and the effective organization of its correction are of great importance. In this regard, it is necessary to clearly define correctional directions and to establish a system of collaboration among all participants in the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. *Defektologiya Prof* [website]. – Moscow, 2021. – URL: <https://www.defektologiya.pro> (accessed: 09.02.2022).
2. Zavadenko, N.N., Rumyantseva, M.V. Dyslexia: mechanisms of development and principles of treatment. *Russian Journal of Child Neurology*. – 2008. – No. 1. – pp. 3–9.
3. Lalaeva, R.I. Reading disorders and ways of their correction in primary school children. – Moscow: Karo, 2019. – 256 p.
4. *Logo-Expert* [website]. – St. Petersburg, 2021. – URL: <https://logopedprofiportal.ru> (accessed: 06.02.2022).
5. Luria, A.R. Higher Cortical Functions in Man. – St. Petersburg: Piter, 2018. – 768 p.
6. Mikhailova, I. Noisy pictures. *Golden Ladder* [website], 2021. – URL: <https://psygazeta.ru/lesenka/razvivashki/159-zashumlennye-kartinki-3.html> (accessed: 10.02.2022).
7. Chirkina, G.V. Theory and practice of overcoming dyslexia – the speech therapy aspect of the problem. *Defektologiya*. – 2007. – No. 1. – pp. 57–58.
8. Zolotkova, E., Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, M.E. Evseyeva (Saransk); Borisova, Y.A., Master’s student. Theoretical and methodological aspects of overcoming dyslexia in primary school children.